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more of my late beloved Charles King provided notwithstanding that in a
 last any of my said nephews or my said great nephews or great nieces or
 shall die before my then day or day share or portions to be equally divided
 between my said surviving nephews and nieces and if the said share
 should be before me then day share or portion of the whole should
 be equally divided between my great nephew and niece Christopher James
 parsons and Charlotte parsons and I hereby give ordain and bequeath all
 my household furniture linen wearing apparel and all other the residue of
 my estate and effects whatsoever and wheresoever to my said niece Charlotte
 parsons and I hereby appoint Eusebius Thomas now residing at the Lodge
 Road and Christopher James parsons of the Great Chamberlain House as
 executors of this my last Will and Testament and so hereby revoke and
 annul all other Will or Wills Covin or Covins by me at any time here-
 fore made and so declare this only to be my last Will and Testament
 in witness whereof I have to this my last Will and Testament written
 in one sheet of paper set my hand this sixth day of March one thousand
 eight hundred and fifty two *Ann King signed and declared by her
 said testatrix Ann King as and for her last Will and Testament in the
 presence of us being present at the same time with at her request in Act a
 presence and in the presence of each other have subscribed our
 names as witnesses* *Thomas Williams Esq. Thomas Street
 Thomas Town Esq. 10 St. George's Street, Suffolk Place, Edgeware Road*

PROVED at London 17th Aug 1853 before the Reverend Frederick Adams
 Pratt Doctor of Laws and Surrogate by the oath of Christopher James parsons
 one of the Executors to whom the same was granted having been first sworn a
 duly to abjure power reserved of making the like grant to Eusebius Thomas the
 other Executor whom he shall apply for the same

*Markham
 Pittor
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In the Name of the Most Holy

and Blessed Trinity Father Son and Holy Ghost the fourteenth day of January
 in the year of our Lord's salvation one thousand eight hundred and forty six
 at the station of Filders Street in the Province of Middlesex the President of
 the Court in the East Indies & *Markham Pittor* Captain in the sixth
 Regiment of Native Infantry attached to the Madras Presidency do hereby of my
 own free will and accord grant give or leave in that it shall please the
 Court to call me (in other words) that I be a natural death or be killed in a
 action or die of my wounds) *All my effects goods monies and matters to my
 present wife in whom I trust Emily Pittor daughter of the late Sir Robert
 Colclough Robert Colclough of the Bengal Army deceased trusting to my said
 wife afore named to make a judicious and equitable distribution of my
 property to my children of Acreby notwithstanding the said Emily Pittor also
 Alexander Colclough Esq. President of the Court of Calcutta in the
 service of the East India Company and a legal establishment likewise my
 brother in law the Reverend John Freeman Rector of the parish of
 St Andrew in the County of Norfolk in the Kingdom of
 England and generally *executors* to this my Will and Testament
 written on the eve of my departure for the Army of the East Indies to journey
 Requiescat in pace and my said wife should be pleased and further have expressed it
 as my wish that my beloved wife should take upon herself the settling any
 debt demands on me of monies borrowed of friends merchants or agents as
 she may find most profitable such liabilities being but trifling at the pre-
 sent time therefore that no part of my property should be sold without her
 consent and I hereby invite all persons indebted to me to come forward under
 a reasonable time to pay their lawful debts to my said wife & Acreby
 in my Acreby property that may be owing to me by the Will or Wills
 of any of my relatives to be allotted in equal portions to my beloved children
 that is if my Will be at all necessary on my part or that of my late
 relatives so to do as in the matter of my affairs with the Government of India
 or the East India Company the Government is in equity in my debt to the*

amount of more than fifteen hundred (Comp^d Dupes / 500.0.0) the claim
 is set up against me on account of some contract my Executors to petition
 Government here and in case of failure thereof to that of the honorable
 the Court of Directors of the East India Company in the matter of my wa
 present appointment & trust there will be no deficiency, nominal or real
 & further hereby constitute my beloved wife my beloved sister Mary
 Freeman and her husband the Reverend John Freeman sole guardians
 of my dear children & further hereby express my desire that should God
 forbid my beloved wife depart before me or after me that the afore men
 tioned Rev^d John Freeman and Dr. Alexander Calmer should upon a
 themselves either or both of them the Office of Executor as before herein
 mentioned lastly I hope and trust that the Executors herein named
 as well as all my sincere friends lay and Clergy will use their best a
 endeavours to cause my dear children to be brought up religiously in
 the blessed faith of our Lord Jesus Christ as entertained and taught
 in the uncorrupt Church of England as established by King Edward and
 James and Queen Elizabeth and all their duty becoming good Christians
 and members of Christ's Church and to pray for me never to converse or
 have suit and to live hereby in charity with all their fellow creatures
 dutiful to their parents their relatives their pastors masters and thus
 may Almighty God thro' his mediation of our Blessed Saviour and
 the Holy Spirit cause them to be blessed eternally
 This fifteenth / 15 / day of January in the year of our Lord one thousand
 eight hundred forty six 1846 Markham Elliot Captain the 1st Bengal
 Regiment of Bengal Infantry D. Signed in our presence. Witness my
 hand and Signature of W. Hill's Capt^l Engineer Signed in our presence
 Witness my hand and Signature of the Master of the Magistrate
 in the Court of Canterbury
 In the goods of Markham Elliot deceased.

Appeared Personally Paul Lynch Willis of the
 Parish of Coburne Saint Mary in the County of Devon Esquire and in a
 oath that he is one of the subscribed witnesses to the last Will and Testament
 now hereto annexed of Markham Elliot late of Coburnham in the
 County of Suffolk formerly a Captain in the 1st Bengal Regiment of Bengal
 Native Infantry but late a Major in the service of the Honourable East
 India Company deceased bearing date at the town of Calcutta the
 fourteenth day of January one thousand eight hundred and forty six and
 at the end thereof the fifteenth day of January one thousand eight
 hundred and forty six and he further made oath that on the said fifteenth
 day of January one thousand eight hundred and forty six the said
 testator duly executed his said Will by signing his names at the foot
 end thereof in manner as now appears hereon in the presence of this
 Appraiser and of Henry Davies the other subscribed witnesses thereto or
 both being then present at the same time and both of whom as to at the
 same time attested and subscribed the said Will in the presence of the
 said testator and of each other and referring to the said Will and as
 observed the memorandum written at the foot or end thereof and as
 below the signatures of the testator and witnesses thereto the same being
 in the words following to wit "This is my last Will and Testament and
 supersedees all other I may ever make to this date 15th Jan^y 1846" &c.
 further made oath that at the time of the execution of the said Will
 as aforesaid the Appraiser observed the said memorandum and is able
 to depose and does depose that the said memorandum was written on
 the said Will and joined part thereof prior to the execution of the said
 Will by the said testator on the aforesaid fifteenth day of January one
 thousand eight hundred and forty six
 Paul Lynch Willis
 sixteenth day of January one thousand eight hundred and fifty three
 this Paul Lynch Willis was duly sworn to the truth thereof by virtue
 of the annexed Commission before me 17th Jan^y 1853. Commissioner

Proved at London the 24th day of August 1753 before me the undersigned
of the Reverend John Freeman Bishop of the Diocese of London
power was granted having been first shown unto me by the said
power reserved of making the like grant to Alexander Chalmer Doctor of
Theology one of the Executors of the said Will apply for the same
Emily Elton Widow the said Will the said Executors and the said
legate in trust named in the said Will and the said Executors the
probate and execution thereof and also the letters of administration
(Will annexed) of the Goods of the said deceased (as by Certificate of Court appears)

This is the last Will of me Henrietta Knight
of No 6 the Polygon in the parish of St. Pauls in the County of Middlesex
Widow of just memory and bequeath all my Real and Personal
estate whatsoever and wheresoever and of what nature or kind soever
unto my grand daughter Hannah Pearce her Heirs and assigns subject
only to the following legacies that is to say to the Reverend Mr. Holt a
one of the Priests of the Roman Catholic Church situate at the Polygon
the sum of one hundred pounds free of legacy duty to be disposed
of as he shall think most agreeable to what would be my wishes and
the interests of the Catholic faith but not to be construed a superstitious
or charitable bequest under the terms of the Statute made of the Seal
and to my servant at present in my service and named Ellen or Abigail
if she shall be living with me at the time of my decease the
sum of ten pounds and to Mr. Russell of the same place free from the debts or
control of her husband's matters and to Mr. Charles Knight of St.
Thomas Lane the sum of one hundred pounds free of legacy duty as a
remuneration for his trouble as Executor of this my Will and of appoint
my sole and lawful Executor of the said Will the said day of April one thousand
eight hundred and fifty three X Signed by the testatrix as and for her
last Will by her cross set opposite to her name which said cross she being
to be her signature and at the same time acknowledged that the said
Will had been previously read and explained to her and that she fully
understood the same and the said testatrix made said cross in the joint
presence of us who in her presence and at her request and in the presence of
each other have hereunto subscribed our names and witnessed to her said
Will the words free of legacy duty having been first twice interpreted in the
presence of us J. C. Payne of 72 Old Broad St. London Solr.
James Perkins & Polygon St. Pauls Church

Henrietta
Knight
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appeared personally James Edwin Payne of
No 7 Old Broad Street in the City of London Solicitor and made oath that
he was present at the execution of and is one of the subscribers or witnesses
to the last Will and Testament of Henrietta Knight formerly of Dorset a
late Regent Park in the late of the Polygon in the parish of Saint Pauls
in the County of Middlesex Widow deceased the said Will being now
unto annexed bearing date the fourth month of April one thousand
eight hundred and fifty three and the deponent further made oath that on
the aforesaid day of the date thereof the said testatrix being executed her
said Will by signing or making her mark or cross at the foot or end thereof
as the same now appears in the presence of him the deponent and of
Thomas Perkins the other subscribed witness thereto both of whom were taken
together at the same time and thereupon the deponent and the said
Thomas Perkins in the presence and at the request of the said testatrix and
also in the presence of each other respectively subscribed their names to the
said Will as witnesses attesting the due execution thereof J. C. Payne
in the fourth month of August one thousand eight hundred and fifty three
the said James Edwin Payne was only sworn to the truth of the
aforesaid affidavit before me W. Robinson Ser. Thos. Nathaniel Roberts